

Algorithmic Bias and Ethical Challenges in AI-Driven Business Decision-Making: A Comparative Perspective Between the U.S. and Africa/MENA

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ABSTRACT

Artificial intelligence (AI) is becoming a powerful tool in business decision-making, offering companies new ways to enhance efficiency, improve predictions, and automate tasks. However, as AI becomes more deeply integrated into business operations, concerns about algorithmic bias and ethical challenges continue to grow. AI models, trained on historical data, can sometimes reinforce biases, leading to unintended consequences in areas such as hiring, financial decision-making, and risk assessment. The way these issues play out differs significantly between developed economies like the United States and emerging markets in Africa and the MENA region.

This paper explores how algorithmic bias affects decision-making in these two different contexts, focusing on key differences in regulations, corporate governance, and the availability of reliable data. In the U.S., businesses operate within established legal frameworks, such as the Equal Credit Opportunity Act and AI ethics guidelines from institutions like the National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST), which encourage accountability and responsible AI use. On the other hand, in Africa and the MENA region, businesses face additional challenges such as limited access to high-quality local data, evolving regulations, and a dependence on AI models developed in Western contexts, which may not always align with local realities. These factors can create inefficiencies, reinforce existing inequalities, and make fair decision-making more difficult.

Through case studies from both regions, this paper highlights the risks associated with AI-driven bias and offers practical recommendations for businesses and policymakers. The findings suggest that strengthening

regulations, promoting locally relevant AI solutions, and emphasizing ethical AI practices can help organizations make better and fairer decisions in the long run.

Key-words :

Algorithmic Bias, Ethical Challenges, AI-Driven Business Decision-Making, A Comparative Perspective, the U.S. Africa/MENA

1. Context of the communication

The accelerated integration of artificial intelligence (AI) into companies' decision-making processes is profoundly changing the way they govern themselves, manage their human resources, manage their risks and their customer relationships. Far from being mere automation tools, AI systems are becoming cognitive actors capable of analysing massive volumes of data, producing predictions and guiding strategic decisions (Brynjolfsson & McAfee, 2017; Haenlein & Kaplan, 2019). However, this automation of decision-making raises major ethical and organisational issues, particularly in relation to the transparency of algorithms, accountability for the results produced, and social justice in access to opportunities (Eubanks, 2018; Cowgill, Dell'Acqua & Deng, 2021).

AI systems are often trained on historical data, which incorporates socio-economic biases or past discrimination, sometimes unconsciously. In the absence of safeguards, these biases can be amplified by predictive models, affecting the quality, fairness and legitimacy of automated decisions (Barocas & Selbst, 2016; Dastin, 2018). These risks are particularly acute in sensitive areas such as recruitment, the granting of credit, the sorting of job applications or customer relationship management.

What's more, these issues are not expressed in the same way on an international scale. In contexts such as the United States and the European Union, AI systems are governed by specific regulations (e.g. the General Data Protection Regulation - GDPR, or the draft AI Act in Europe), as well as by technical and ethical standards developed by specialist bodies (e.g. NIST, 2023). These environments also have a wealth of expertise enabling AI uses to be calibrated in line with societal issues (Floridi & Cowls, 2019).

On the other hand, in many countries in Africa and the MENA region, AI is being deployed in contexts where regulations are still fragmentary or non-existent (Zwitter et al., 2020; Njie & Asongu, 2022). Added to this is a growing technological dependence on imported solutions, which are often poorly adapted to local realities (language, culture, data, infrastructure). The scarcity of reliable and representative data is a major obstacle to algorithmic sovereignty in these countries, limiting their ability to develop ethical, inclusive and appropriate systems (Taylor, 2017).

This discrepancy creates a systemic risk: that of 'algorithmic colonisation', where automated decisions are imposed on populations without the possibility of adjustment or challenge, potentially exacerbating existing inequalities rather than reducing them (Birhane, 2021). In the absence of robust public policies, structured data governance and participatory technology design, AI may become a vector of socio-technical imbalances and managerial inequity in southern countries.

2. Academic and interest

2.1 Academic interest in research and universities

From a scientific point of view, this paper is at the crossroads of several contemporary debates in management science, technology ethics and development economics. Firstly, it questions the universality of artificial intelligence models, which are often designed in Western socio-economic contexts (United States, Europe) and then deployed on a global scale without sufficient adjustment to local realities. This raises fundamental questions about the transferability of decision-making technologies, the reproducibility of algorithmic results, and the differentiated socio-economic effects depending on the territory (Birhane, 2021; Zicari et al., 2022).

Secondly, the study adopts a North/South comparative approach, which is relatively little used in empirical work on algorithmic governance. By comparing the structured legal and ethical framework of the United States with the emerging contexts of Africa and the MENA region, it highlights the differences in maturity, technological sovereignty and data infrastructures. It thus contributes to documenting a structural asymmetry in the production and implementation of AI systems, joining the growing concerns around algorithmic justice, data governance and digital sovereignty (Taylor, 2017; Zwitter et al., 2020).

Finally, this research feeds into the emerging literature on ethical and responsible AI in developing countries (Cowls et al., 2021). It highlights the need for a strong contextualisation of algorithmic models and opens the way to research perspectives rooted in Southern epistemologies (Santos, 2014), capable of going beyond the dominant paradigms centred on Silicon Valley.

2.2 Managerial interest for companies and stakeholders

For decision-makers, this research provides tangible elements for a better understanding of the operational, reputational and social risks associated with the unsupervised use of AI. In particular, it draws attention to the mechanisms of algorithmic unfairness likely to directly affect the processes of recruitment, credit allocation, customer scoring or human resources guidance (Eubanks, 2018; Cowgill et al., 2021).

It also highlights the need to adapt AI tools to local contexts: AI that is effective in the United States can have perverse effects in an African country if it is based on incomplete data, culturally inappropriate variables, or an optimisation logic that is not shared. This inadequacy can lead to inefficiencies, internal resistance and a loss of confidence among stakeholders.

On a more operational level, this study proposes concrete avenues for strengthening the acceptability and ethics of AI systems: integration of internal ethics committees, auditability of algorithms, raising team awareness, shared governance of data, and development of more inclusive hybrid models. It is therefore a strategic lever for any organisation wishing to combine digital transformation and social responsibility (Floridi & Cowls, 2019).

3. Central issue

While artificial intelligence promises to make managerial decisions more streamlined, its real effects depend very much on the contexts in which it is designed, deployed and interpreted. While AI systems in industrialised countries benefit from relatively robust ethical regulations and control mechanisms, the situation is very different in emerging economies, where data governance, infrastructures and local standards are still under construction.

This asymmetry raises a central question:

To what extent can the use of artificial intelligence systems, often designed in Western contexts, produce biased, unfair or counter-productive decisions when applied to managerial environments in Africa and in the MENA region, and what ethical, organisational and regulatory responses can help mitigate these risks?

This question highlights a double paradox:

- The paradox of technological performance vs. contextual relevance: AI can be technically powerful but culturally inappropriate, producing decisions that are disconnected from local realities.

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- The paradox of algorithmic neutrality: presented as objective, AI is in fact based on data and modelling logics that are deeply situated, likely to reproduce or amplify pre-existing inequalities.

This deliberately cross-cutting questioning is part of a desire to examine the logic of technological importation without contextualisation and its consequences on decision-making justice and the governance of organisations. In order to refine the analysis, three sub-questions have been selected, each responding to a structuring dimension of the phenomenon under study.

3.1 Technical sub-issue: transferability of AI models

To what extent can artificial intelligence systems designed in Western contexts produce decision-making biases when applied to African or MENA environments with different socio-economic and informational realities?

This first area aims to examine the portability of algorithmic models and their ability to process local data, which is often absent, fragmented or incomplete, in an accurate and relevant manner. The choice of this question is based on an empirical observation: many AI solutions used in developing countries are imported without any structural adaptation to contextual variables. This poses a crucial challenge in terms of data reliability and representativeness, with the potential consequence of erroneous or exclusionary decisions. This issue is closely linked to the theory of socio-technical systems and data governance.

3.2. Ethical sub-question: the risks of discrimination and algorithmic injustice

What types of injustice or discrimination can emerge from automated decisions based on opaque or ill-adapted algorithms, and how can they be anticipated through an ethical approach rooted in local realities?

This second area is fundamental to assessing the social effects of automated decisions, particularly in areas with a high degree of human sensitivity (recruitment, credit rating, sorting of job applications). It opens up a field of critical reflection on the logic of indirect discrimination, which is sometimes invisible in algorithmic chains, but which can amplify existing inequalities. The choice of this sub-question is in line with work on algorithmic justice (Barocas & Selbst, 2016; Eubanks, 2018) and a desire to reconcile technological performance and social justice. It also questions the forms of explicability, accountability and contestability of AI decisions.

3.3. Institutional and managerial sub-issues: governance and adaptation levers

What mechanisms for regulation, data governance and managerial adaptation can be mobilised to provide a framework for the use of AI in African and MENA companies, while strengthening their technological sovereignty?

The third area completes the analysis by looking at the organisational, regulatory and institutional capacities for technological absorption. The aim here is to explore the practical conditions for ensuring that AI is more responsible and better contextualised, by mobilising mechanisms for regulation, participation and ethical governance. This line of questioning responds to the need not to reduce reflection to technological criticism, but to open up realistic and localised perspectives for action. It resonates with institutional theory and stakeholder theory, emphasising the collective appropriation of AI tools.

4. Theoretical framework

The study of algorithmic biases and ethical issues related to artificial intelligence (AI) in corporate decision-making processes calls for a theoretical mobilisation that is both plural and critical. Through a comparative approach between North American contexts and those of African and MENA countries, we articulate five complementary theoretical frameworks. Each allows us to grasp an essential dimension of the issue, while offering an analytical framework adapted to different contexts.

4.1. Algorithmic justice theory (Barocas & Selbst, 2016; Dastin, 2018)

The theory of algorithmic justice is concerned with studying the forms of inequity produced or reproduced by artificial intelligence systems, particularly when these are based on biased historical data. It examines the ability of algorithms to treat individuals from different social groups fairly, taking into account the social, economic and cultural conditions of access to digital resources.

A Moroccan microfinance company using a solvency analysis algorithm developed in the United States systematically excludes informal customers with no banking history, even though they are solvent. This case illustrates a structural bias caused by a lack of contextual adaptation of the discriminating variables. The algorithm, perceived as 'objective', actually becomes a factor of silent injustice, underlining the importance of algorithmic justice as a framework for critical vigilance.

4.2. Institutional theory (North, 1990; DiMaggio & Powell, 1983)

Institutional theory enables us to analyse how regulatory structures, social norms, cultural practices and governance arrangements influence the adoption of technologies. It is central in a comparative perspective, as it reveals the disparities between highly regulated environments, such as the United States, and emerging or unstable institutional contexts in Africa and the MENA region.

In the United States, the use of AI in credit rating is governed by laws such as the Equal Credit Opportunity Act, while in Senegal, a fintech is implementing an algorithm without a clear legal framework. This institutional asymmetry allows the company to collect sensitive personal data without any guarantee of transparency, exposing users to risks of discrimination and surveillance. Institutional theory helps us to understand the crucial role of normative environments in the ethical regulation of AI.

4.3. Stakeholder theory (Freeman, 1984; Freeman et al., 2007)

This theory introduces a relational logic into managerial analysis, positing that the performance and legitimacy of companies depend on the recognition and integration of the interests of all their stakeholders. In the case of AI, this means considering the impact of algorithmic systems on a range of stakeholders: employees, customers, regulators, NGOs and local communities.

In Egypt, a recruitment platform uses an AI pre-selection tool based on gendered databases. Local NGOs revealed a systemic under-representation of women in the applications received. In response, the company set up a multi-stakeholder ethics committee including representatives from civil society. This reaction reflects the fact that stakeholders are taken into account as a vector for ethical correction, in accordance with the precepts of this theory.

4.4. Sociotechnical systems theory (Trist & Bamforth, 1951; Leonardi, 2011)

This theory postulates that any technology is co-constructed with the social and organisational environments into which it is inserted. The effectiveness of a system cannot be assessed independently of its human appropriation, its local uses, or its compatibility with existing routines and values. In this way, we can understand the gaps between technical performance and social acceptability.

In Tunisia, a public administration introduced an HR chatbot in standard Arabic. Employees, accustomed to direct exchanges and dialect language, rejected the tool en masse. Despite its technical capabilities, AI failed to become part of the socio-organisational fabric, due to a lack of cultural and linguistic adaptation. This case illustrates the importance of analysing AI systems not as neutral technical objects, but as socio-technical artefacts embedded in human contexts.

4.5. Data governance theory (Khatri & Brown, 2010; Otto, 2011)

Data governance deals with the rules, processes and responsibilities that govern the collection, management, access and security of data. In the context of AI, it is a fundamental lever for guaranteeing the reliability, traceability and ethics of algorithmic models, particularly in contexts where digital infrastructures are weak or fragmented.

A Kenyan fintech is using behavioural data from smartphones to score loan applications. This data, stored on servers located outside the African continent, is not subject to any national regulation. This case highlights the lack of algorithmic sovereignty: the quality of AI decisions depends directly on data governance, which is often unevenly distributed between North and South.

These five interacting theories enable us to understand algorithmic biases not as mere technical anomalies, but as the products of differentiated historical, institutional, social and political contexts. They reveal that the fundamental issue is not AI per se, but the conditions under which it is implemented, legitimised and regulated in asymmetrical environments.

The illustrations provided show that behind each algorithm deployed there is a delicate balance between innovation, equity and sovereignty. Understanding these mechanisms is an essential prerequisite for promoting truly inclusive and responsible AI in the countries of Africa and the MENA region.

5. Comparative analysis of algorithmic dynamics: USA vs Africa/MENA

To answer our question, we propose a comparative and contextualised reading of the issues linked to the use of artificial intelligence systems in corporate decision-making processes. This comparison highlights not only differences in technological maturity, but also profound differences in the way AI is designed, regulated, governed and used. The focus is on three areas of analysis: algorithm development and training models, the social effects of AI decisions, and institutional mechanisms for regulation and ethical governance.

5.1. Origin and calibration of AI models: between technological autonomy and structural dependence

In the United States, companies have extensive access to large volumes of structured, historical data, governed by specific regulations. These resources enable them to train artificial intelligence models in a controlled manner, fine-tuning the variables according to their strategic objectives (Haenlein & Kaplan,

2019). Algorithms are generally designed in-house, or delegated to technology giants with advanced expertise in machine learning, guaranteeing a degree of control over the development process.

This ability to audit and correct models in the event of drift is illustrated by the case of Amazon, which had designed an application pre-selection algorithm for its HR departments. When a gender bias was detected - the tool systematically disadvantaged female profiles - the company was able to identify the source of the problem, suspend use of the model, and publicly take responsibility for it (Dastin, 2018). This type of rapid reaction can be explained by the existence of a normative and technical environment that enables AI systems to be effectively supervised.

Conversely, in Africa and the MENA region, companies operate in environments where digital infrastructures, reliable local data and regulatory mechanisms are often lacking. Algorithmic models are mostly imported, trained on Western datasets that reflect neither the social practices nor the economic realities of local users. This structural maladjustment severely limits the capacity for contextual adaptation. The case of a Moroccan fintech illustrates this eloquently: using a customer scoring model based on digital behaviour (frequency of online purchases, mobile browsing, use of social networks), the company found that rural women, despite being creditworthy within informal community networks, were systematically excluded from access to credit. These profiles, absent from the model's digital repositories, become invisible to the algorithm. This phenomenon leads to automated, silent exclusion, with no possibility of challenge, revealing the profound limits of non-contextualised AI.

5.2. Social effects and perceptions of algorithmic decisions: between legitimisation and rejection

In advanced economies, the decisions produced by artificial intelligence systems generally form part of a legal, cultural and institutional ecosystem that promotes transparency, accountability and the right to challenge. Users have mechanisms at their disposal for questioning algorithmic results, requesting justifications and asserting their right to an explanation, particularly in the context of the right to explanation provided for by the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). These legal and technical guarantees help to strengthen the social legitimacy of AI in the public arena, by providing safeguards against the potentially discriminatory effects of automated systems.

This principle is embodied, for example, in the banking sector in the United States, where a financial institution using a credit scoring algorithm is required, in the event of a refusal, to explain the criteria that led to the decision. This requirement for transparency reduces the perceived arbitrariness, reinforces user confidence and fuels a dynamic of democratic control of technological tools. Conversely, in many countries in Africa and the MENA region, the institutional environment remains ill-equipped to provide a framework for the use of AI, whether in terms of regulation, digital education or appeal mechanisms. The opacity of algorithmic models, combined with low technological literacy and the absence of mediation bodies, is fuelling growing mistrust of automated decisions, and even a rejection of their legitimacy.

An emblematic case can be seen in Tunisia, where a public administration has introduced an intelligent virtual assistant responsible for processing requests for internal mobility. Although technically effective, the tool was quickly challenged by staff: it was perceived as impersonal, dehumanising and opaque in its operation. The sense of injustice generated by the absence of clear explanations and the lack of human dialogue eventually led to widespread resistance to the system, revealing the need to integrate technologies into governance systems that are adapted to local cultural and social expectations.

5.3. Regulation and governance: between an institutionalised framework and a legal vacuum

In the United States, the regulation of artificial intelligence systems is still a work in progress, but it is already based on a robust and evolving body of legislation. Measures such as the Equal Credit Opportunity Act, the NIST AI Risk Management Framework (2023), and the obligations arising from the European RGPD for multinationals operating internationally, are laying the foundations for a technical and ethical framework for AI. The principle of accountability - the explicit responsibility of organisations for algorithmic decisions - has now been integrated into the management culture of many companies, notably through internal audit practices and algorithmic impact assessments.

This proactive governance approach is being put into practice in a number of major US firms. A growing number of Fortune 500 companies have set up AI ethics committees, made up of lawyers, data scientists, human resources representatives and civil society representatives. The role of these multi-disciplinary bodies is to assess the risks associated with the models used, anticipate biases and ensure that practices are compatible with social responsibility and diversity standards.

On the other hand, in African and MENA countries, the institutional framework remains largely underdeveloped, both in terms of regulation and organisational governance. The absence of specific laws on AI, combined with technological dependence on international private players, leaves a normative vacuum that facilitates the introduction of algorithmic systems without supervision mechanisms or accountability procedures.

A striking example is that of a Senegalese e-commerce platform that has integrated an algorithmic recommendation engine to optimise product visibility. In the absence of technical supervision or explicit weighting criteria, this engine systematically favours sellers capable of producing visually attractive content (high-definition photos, detailed product sheets, regularity of stocks). Small rural retailers, who are active but less digitalised, are thus relegated to the margins of the system, reducing their commercial visibility and, ultimately, their economic inclusion.

This type of drift highlights a deeper reality: artificial intelligence is becoming a mirror that amplifies asymmetries in development. Whereas, in Western contexts, algorithmic biases are often identified, debated and, in some cases, corrected, in African/MENA environments they are internalised, naturalised or even invisible, due to a lack of warning structures, critical tools or autonomous regulatory capacity. AI cannot therefore be seen as a neutral or universal tool. On the contrary, it crystallises profound systemic imbalances, posing an urgent challenge for academic research, public policy and managerial strategies in developing countries.

6. Towards differentiated North/South convergence

At the end of this comparative analysis, it is clear that the ethical deployment of AI in managerial decisions cannot be based on a universal model. It requires differentiated, contextualised but interoperable responses that take account of institutional maturity, organisational realities and structural asymmetries. We propose below a series of recommendations based on three axes: design and training of AI models, ethical framework and governance, and development of organisational capabilities.

6.1. Towards a contextual and inclusive design of AI systems

One of the first levers for truly responsible artificial intelligence lies in reconfiguring the design logic of algorithmic models, ensuring that they are contextualised, inclusive and adaptable to the diversity of application environments. This requirement cannot be met by a one-size-fits-all approach; it calls for differentiated responses between technologically advanced countries and emerging economies.

In the countries of the North, particularly in the United States and Europe, technology companies and research institutions are called upon to engage in co-production processes with stakeholders in the South. This involves not only integrating data from territories that are often absent from the learning corpus, but also incorporating relevant socio-cultural variables, local languages and usage patterns that are specific to these contexts. The aim of this cooperative movement is to reduce the algorithmic divide and avoid the reproduction of hegemonic models that are disconnected from local realities. It is also important to promote the use of ethically sourced, diversified and collaboratively annotated datasets, in order to prevent the over-representation of certain dominant profiles or the algorithmic exclusion of minority groups (Barocas & Selbst, 2016; Zicari et al., 2022). In addition, multi-criteria audit systems should be integrated upstream of deployment, including indicators of systemic bias, intergroup equity and explanatory capacity (explicability). In African and MENA countries, where technical resources may be more limited, the priority is to create hybrid models, combining local data, participatory approaches and community intelligence. Crowdsourcing, citizen observatories and open data initiatives can go some way to compensating for the lack of data collection infrastructure. It is also recommended that structured, locally-governed databases be set up in partnership with universities, local authorities and NGOs, in order to guarantee both the quality of the data and sovereignty over its use. Finally, "off-the-shelf" algorithmic systems or systems imported without adjustment must undergo a compulsory contextualisation phase, including empirical validation in the field, in order to avoid automatic exclusion effects and the mechanical reproduction of unsuitable foreign standards.

Thus, the design of responsible and inclusive AI requires not a vertical transfer of technological solutions, but a collaborative logic of co-innovation, where local relevance and global equity are considered as intrinsic criteria of algorithmic performance.

6.2. Strengthening ethical regulation and algorithmic governance mechanisms

The ethical governance of artificial intelligence systems is a major strategic challenge today. Faced with the growing risks of bias, opacity or abuse in decision-making linked to AI, it is becoming imperative to build differentiated but articulated regulatory frameworks capable of ensuring a balance between technological innovation, social responsibility and digital sovereignty. Here again, the responses to be provided will vary according to the level of regulatory maturity, institutional traditions and operational capabilities of the contexts concerned.

In the countries of the North, notably the United States and Europe, existing regulations such as the European AI Act and the NIST AI Risk Management Framework are already laying the foundations for a regulatory framework. However, to meet the challenges of algorithmic justice on a global scale, it is becoming necessary to extend these mechanisms to international interactions, by imposing minimum ethical clauses on exported technologies, particularly when they are deployed in fragile contexts. Companies developing AI solutions with a global reach should set up internal algorithmic governance committees, including not only technical and legal experts, but also representatives of stakeholders affected by the use of algorithms - including those from the global South. In addition, sector-specific ethical certification of algorithms, based on criteria of

transparency, non-discrimination and accountability, could be a powerful lever of legitimisation for both companies and users.

In the countries of the South, and more particularly in Africa and the MENA region, the challenges are twofold: they involve both laying the foundations for an appropriate legal framework and developing structures capable of implementing these rules. This means gradually developing national or regional regulatory frameworks that take account of local socio-political and legal realities, while drawing on international best practice. At the same time, the creation of multi-sector consultative bodies, bringing together public, private, academic and community players, would enable the ethical, economic and social impact of the technologies deployed to be analysed. Finally, it is essential to train local auditors specialising in algorithmic ethics, who can act as a critical interface between technical operators, end users and public institutions. These hybrid profiles, who are both rooted in their local area and skilled in technological matters, would be the guarantors of a truly responsibly governed AI. So, whether it's a question of consolidating existing regulations or building new ones, strengthening algorithmic governance necessarily involves multi-level cooperation, procedural transparency and the inclusion of local players in the very design of supervisory systems.

6.3. Developing managerial skills and capabilities in the face of AI

The growing integration of artificial intelligence into organisations requires, over and above the technical and regulatory dimensions, a major investment in human skills, particularly managerial skills. Indeed, decision-makers are called upon to evolve in complex technological environments, marked by increasingly opaque algorithmic logic, and to assume new responsibilities linked to ethics, data governance and the legitimacy of automated decisions. This transformation calls for a redefinition of knowledge, attitudes and management tools, depending on the resources available and the priorities of each context.

In northern countries, where companies and institutions have advanced training infrastructures, it is recommended that specific training programmes in algorithmic ethics management be rolled out. These programmes should go beyond technical considerations to include modules on social justice, cultural diversity, systemic bias and the contextualisation of AI models. In addition, it is essential to include indicators relating to social sustainability in the tools used to assess the performance of algorithmic systems: the level of inclusion of target audiences, the impact on the diversity of the profiles selected, and the trust perceived by users. Finally, organisations in the North have a key role to play in supporting research-action initiatives carried out with partners in the South, in order to co-develop algorithmic innovations that are participatory, contextualised and meaningful at a local level.

In the countries of the South, and particularly in Africa and the MENA region, efforts must focus on building local capacity to interact with technologies. Hybrid training courses need to be designed for managers, public officials and entrepreneurs, combining an introduction to AI, digital law and data governance. At the same time, it is crucial to promote a culture of algorithmic contestability within organisations: employees must be able to question an AI decision, understand the criteria behind it, and benefit from accessible explanation mechanisms. This ability to "debate with algorithms" is a way of democratising the technology. Finally, it is proposed to create centres of excellence in inclusive AI, attached to universities and local authorities, and dedicated to social innovation, training and local experimentation with ethical solutions. These centres would be a strategic lever for anchoring artificial intelligence in the economic, linguistic and cultural realities of the societies concerned.

The development of skills should therefore not be seen simply as technical support, but as a central dimension of algorithmic sovereignty. It conditions the ability of players to direct the use of AI towards fair, sustainable and locally appropriate ends.

Conclusion

The irruption of artificial intelligence into the decision-making sphere is not just a technological turning point: it is an epistemological, organisational and ethical turning point. By reconfiguring the ways in which decisions are selected, evaluated and steered within companies, AI is becoming an instrument of algorithmic power, the real effects of which depend less on its computing power than on the way in which it is designed, deployed and governed.

Our paper highlighted a fundamental tension: that between the universalisation of AI models and the diversity of the socio-economic contexts in which they operate. Through a comparative analysis between the United States and the countries of Africa/MENA, we have shown that algorithmic biases do not result solely from technical errors, but from structural discrepancies in the design, regulation and appropriation of AI tools.

In advanced economies, automated decisions are part of a system of ethical supervision, technical auditability and institutional accountability. Conversely, in African and MENA countries, the absence of regulation, dependence on imported systems and the fragility of local data accentuate the risks of silent discrimination, loss of technological sovereignty and cultural disconnection.

Faced with this asymmetry, our contribution stresses the need for 'differentiated convergence': developing AI practices that are ethical, responsible and contextually rooted, by combining international standards with local roots. This implies:

- A transformation of algorithmic design logic towards more co-construction and contextual hybridisation;
- Strengthening institutional capacities for regulation and ethical supervision in emerging countries;
- And support for managerial staff in developing a reflective algorithmic culture, based on explicability, contestability and social justice.

Beyond technologies, this reflection opens the way to ambitious research into the conditions for the emergence of an AI that is fair, plural and genuinely shared - in which the countries of the South would no longer be mere testing grounds, but sovereign players in algorithmic innovation.

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